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IMPROVING LESSON EFFICIENCY THROUGH MODERN DIDACTIC GAMES IN TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF HORSES IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract. This article talks about the importance of modern educational and didactic games in teaching the noun phrase in primary class mother tongue classes.

Key words: Vocabulary, method, Alphabet chain, Cinquain, exercises.

Enter: Today, radical improvement of the education sector has become the demand of the times. The development of the education system in our country from the first years of the perspective has risen to the level of state policy, ensuring that our children acquire modern knowledge and skills in conditions corresponding to world standards, grow up as physically and spiritually mature people, their abilities and great work is being done to realize the talent and intellectual potential of our youth, to perfect the feelings of loyalty to the motherland.

Research materials and methodology

Consistency is very important in teaching the subject of "Horse" in primary grades. Because students acquire knowledge about this vocabulary step by step. The preparatory stage of teaching nouns corresponds to the period of literacy training. During this period, students learn to differentiate between people and things. Emphasis is placed on lexical meanings, grouping skills are formed. In the 2nd grade, knowledge about common and similar nouns will be deepened. To form the concept of "noun", it is of great importance to divide the nouns belonging to this word group into main lexical groups, to show the characteristics of all nouns in our speech. For this purpose, in the first lessons devoted to the study of the subject, words denoting persons and things are put into one system, people, things, words denoting plants and natural phenomena are divided into groups. Signs common to all these words are identified: these words are persons, who is referring to things? or what? there will be an answer to the question.

Research results

The tasks of learning a horse in elementary grades are as follows:

1. Formation of grammatical concepts about "noun".
2. who? What is the answer to the question? paralyze the ability to distinguish nouns that are the answer to a question

Discussion

We can use the following methods to teach the noun group to primary classes:

Method 1. Alphabet chain. In this method, students need to use words related to nouns. The purpose of the method is that it encourages students to focus on one place, and is effective in reinforcing the topic. The game is played in the following order:

1. The game is organized in the form of a chain and everyone participates;
2. The first student says: "I bought an orange from the store."

3. The second student repeats the same sentence, but instead of orange, he should put a word related to the group of nouns starting with the letter B. Because the letter A is followed by the letter B in the alphabet. For example: "I bought a banana from the store." The word banana beginning with the letter B is used here. Banana is a noun.

4. The game continues like this. The one who deviates from the order is the loser.

Method 2. Three-in-one method. This method can be used to reinforce the "Happy moment" or the topic. The method can be used in other subjects as well. The teacher combines 3 activities through one method. Students write by thinking, thinking and searching. They enjoy thinking about the word they read, remembering, thinking, gesturing. When using the method, pieces of paper and a box are needed. The method is executed in the following order:

- At first, the cut pieces of paper are distributed to the students;
- Within 1 minute, students must write words related to 1 noun phrase on the paper;
- They should fold the papers and put them in a box.
- The words in the box are scrambled.
- One student goes to the board and takes 1 piece of paper and expresses it using a non-verbal gesture;
- The rest of the students need to find these words.
- The student who found it goes to the board and the game continues in this way.

Method 3. See and remember method. This method is effective if the teacher uses it in 1-2 grades. Because it is difficult for 1st and 2nd graders to concentrate. The method is executed in the following order:

- 1 student from each group is selected to participate in the game;
- Each student is shown a variety of pictures;
- The teacher shows 7-8 pictures related to noun phrases. For example: apple, book, flower, pencil, comb, snow, computer and hakazo;
- Students must remember the pictures;
- These pictures are shown to the rest of the students, who test their memory even if they are not participating in the game.

The game is played in this order. Students who get the most correct answers are encouraged.

Method 4. Sinkwain method. It is advisable to use the sinkwain method in 4th grades. Because it is a bit difficult. Cinquain is a French word meaning "poem of five lines".

The method rule is as follows:

- one word is written in the first line (referring to the noun group);
- in the second line, the subject is described with two words (referring to the adjective word group);
- in the third line, the behavior on this topic is described in three words;
- in the fourth line, write a sentence consisting of four words indicating the relevance to the topic;
- in the fifth line, a synonym corresponding to the essence of the topic is written.

Example:

Teacher

Knowledgeable, kind

Teaches, teaches, cares

The greatest breed in the world

Tutor.

Summary

So, didactic methods in teaching nouns in primary grades serve to further increase the student's educational and cognitive activity

References:

1. R. Yoldoshev, R. Khusainova, U. Bobojonova. Interactive methods of education (methodical manual). Urganch-2011.
2. Methodology of mother tongue teaching. K. Kasimova, S. Matchonov, Kh. Gulomova, Sh. Yoldosheva, Sh. Sariyev.-T.: "PUBLISHER", 2009.